

Migration, Displacement and Ethnicity: A Complex Conundrum in Northeast India

Dr. Kathiresan Loganathan¹

Dr. Ratna Huirem²

Humans have been migrating over millennia. The quest for simple food and suitable habitat determined migration then, and hence was more voluntary. Today, the scenario is vastly different. The lines between voluntary and forced migration are blurred. Even if one is not forcibly evicted, inability to access basic goods and services in the globalised world brings in the element of compulsion. The wrath of nature, propelled mostly by man's actions upon it, have intensified ecological disasters. Conflicts over who should belong where, mar the functioning of a peaceful society. Vast development projects rattle the fragile ecology of the region, resulting in displacement. The complex history of the northeast is inundated with immigration through its porous borders. Contest over scarce resources resulted in a multitude of disgruntlement embedded in ethnicity. This paper is conceptualised in this background. It examines the interface between migration and displacement and locates the ethnic character that underlines the northeast.

Migration and Displacement

Migration is an all-pervasive phenomenon today. Martin (2013) had noted an estimated 230 million international migrants across the globe in 2013 and this number will doubly grow by 2050. The study also talks about the even larger scale of migration within their own countries. It enlists urbanization, climate change and armed conflict as major drivers. The works of De Sherbinin, et al., (2008) and Oglethorpe, et al., (2007) are also noted therein where they examine human migration and its potential to bring about rapid changes in terms of its population size and density; much beyond those stemming from fertility and mortality. The notion of time and space underlining this complex demographic concept are also highlighted (Kallio, 2016).

The United Nations (1958) Multilingual Demographic Dictionary connotes migration as a kind of mobility involving different geographical spaces, usually necessitating giving up the old place of residence for a new one. However, migration cannot be termed as a mere shifting of residence. Social relationships and the social context of the area is also crucial. Thus G. S. Gosal points out that migration is a process that can impact; a) the new

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Social Work, Assam University Silchar.

² Assistant Professor, Department of Social Work, Assam University Silchar.

environment b) the old environment and c) the migrants themselves (Gosal, 1961, as cited in Shimray & Devi, 2009).

Migration and displacement are like the two sides of a coin and go hand in hand. One migrates because one is displaced from his home environment and is in search of a new environment that will be relatively more secure in terms of his life and livelihood. This is where the socio-economic and political factors come into play. Moreover, not only does displacement induce migration. The act of migration itself also results in displacement as one does not 'feel at home' in the new environment. Hence, displacement is both a cause and consequence. Migration is the process or act of trying to cover up the loss.

Kearns and Mason (2013) emphasize that the terms 'forced relocation' and 'displacement' are insufficient to portray the complex processes involved therein. They add that existing studies focus more on physical relocation but the social and/ or psychosocial aspects are ignored often. Moreover, the context of space and time are also of extreme significance. The United Nations (2004) in its Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement, highlighted the similarity between people displaced thus and of refugees. Compulsive forces are making a set of the population relocate/ flee, owing to armed conflict-induced, human rights violations, as well as natural and man-made disasters.

Referring to social displacement, they raise the concern that those leaving a place suffer from diminished 'social networks', and other social 'support mechanisms' in their new environment. Psychological displacement occurs owing to forcible forfeiture of their homelands (Fried, 1963, as cited in Kearns and Mason, 2013), unfamiliar neighbourhoods, and a loss of identity. Reduced community feeling, mistrust, diminished status, inability to 'fit in', a lesser degree of attachment with the new environment are the various problems faced.

The Northeast Conundrum

The problem of migration and displacement in the northeast region (NER) is an intricately woven web of complexities. Conflicts, disasters, economic development etc., are the myriad issues that plague the region. However, a lot of these are steeped in history. Dasgupta and Dey (2010) report that understanding conflict-borne displacement in the NER necessitates understanding the historical background of the cartographies of the region. Political underpinnings and arbitrariness shaped these cartographies leaving out the region's actors. Thus, the celebration of a free India did not augur well

in the NER as the seeds of conflict were thus sown. To this day, armed rebellion for self-determination and independence mars the economic development and peace in the region. They further highlight how the common notions of push and pull factors cannot exemplify migration and displacement in the NER. Rather, the notions of ‘legality’ and ‘illegality’ were underlined. This point is very significant in the context of the porous border of the NER. Hence, understanding the finer nuances of migration, displacement and forced migration in the backdrop of the uniqueness of the region is emphasized.

Nath (2005) also argues that undocumented immigration to the NER has aggravated the problem. The region has been forced to be home to immigrants from the adjoining nations of Bangladesh, Nepal, and Myanmar. These range from both legal to illegal. It resulted in a huge surge of the population from around one million to more than 20 million over the past century. Thus, the competition for resources and other opportunities rose. The perception of the migrant communities as the ‘other’ who snatched away opportunities resulted in socio-political upheavals and ethnic clashes. Anti-outsider movements dotted the NER. Assam was the epitome of such a scenario. The ‘son of the soil’ agitation in Assam (Nath, 2005), also known as the Assam Movement, 1979-85, served as the impetus for many such subsequent movements in the rest of the NER. Identity politics thus defined the postcolonial political agenda. The movements aimed at overthrowing the ‘illegal’ immigrants and their ingress to the region many times backfired on the indigenous people too as the distinction between indigenous and foreign groups were unclear. Many times, civilians bore the brunt of such clashes as entire villages have been razed to the ground to force the ‘other’ to vacate disputed territories. Consequently, innocent people move to horrific conditions in displacement camps. Thus, the saga of displacement goes on in the NER.

Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in the NER

IDPs are those who have been compelled to abandon their home environments owing to armed conflicts, violation of human rights, or disasters. However, they have not crossed an international border. The long-lasting and severe impacts of such displacement not only affect individuals and their households, but even society as a whole (Nath, 2005). As the responsibility buck passes on, administration of immediate relief and rehabilitation measures are often subsumed by petty politics. The NER stands to lose further as both national and international media shy away from its reportage. Journalists face challenging situations in covering the region. The media is controlled by a variety of state and non-state actors that impinge upon them. Besides, such

stories require follow up which is often impossible. And most importantly, mainstream media does not care much about migration stories as it is considered a non-profitable pursuit.

People in the NER suffer from a barrage of internal displacements induced by conflict, environment, and development; cutting across all backgrounds and regions. The degree is just higher for the poor and marginalised. Weak government interventions worsen the scenario. Forced migration is the norm for those thus displaced. They highlight the need for research underscoring the need for effective policies to uphold the rights of these victims. The uniquely heterogeneous character of the region, where transport and communication continue to be a challenge in most of its hinterlands, must be recognized (Dasgupta and Dey, 2010).

Another important aspect is that migration of such a forceful kind is largely reliant on networks of the migrants themselves. The significance of the role of legislations is also highlighted. A unique proposition is that of a historical atlas of migration in the region. The inefficacy of relying on the social sciences to fully examine and understand the complexities of migration and displacement in the backdrop of partition is yet another issue. Changing landscape, intra and inter-ethnic conflicts, and memories of a lost homeland plague the people of the region. Poor media coverage of the lives of these subalterns worsens things. A spontaneous resort to militarization in the name of securing lives completes the downfall (Dasgupta and Dey, 2010).

Hussain (2005) adds value to the above arguments through estimates that more than three million people had been displaced in the recent past when the Brahmaputra was in spate. Dams that have paid scant attention to the fragility of the region's ecology have also wreaked havoc by increasing earthquake tremors. These displaced people are mostly tribals who survive on the fringes of their familiar ecology. They then go on to lead abysmal lives in camps with little or no medical care and minimal education for the children. Thus, the vicious circle of landlessness, homelessness, joblessness, social isolation, and exclusion envelopes them. An adoption of definite and unambiguous IDP policies based on the UN Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement is proposed.

The Geneva-based Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC)'s near-real-time displacement monitoring tool showed Assam as the only place where people continued to live in camps much after the disaster has ebbed away. So, the aftermath is highly significant. On April 30, there were some 16,370 people living in displacement. During the last five years

(2018-2022, May), at any point of time, around 20,000 people had lived in camps, displaced by disasters. Most of them spent an average of 5-6 months in such relief camps (DownToEarth, 2022).

Upadhyay (2005) further lends credence to the above viewpoints. She stated that the unabated movement of people from erstwhile East Bengal, now referred to as Bangladesh, to different parts of the NER has resulted in a natural reformation of the region along ethnic, linguistic, and religious lines. This undoubtedly spawned a multitude of tensions in the region along these lines, which are all interrelated. She also clarifies that such an ongoing influx can be attributed to these same reasons, although it seems paradoxical. Millions of Hindus fled from East Bengal to India to seek refuge during the post-partition saga. Yet again, almost 10 million Bengalis sought shelter in India during the Bangladesh liberation war, 1971. Additionally, thousands of Chakmas rushed to India to escape ethnic conflicts in the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) around the same decade. All these created a cumulative effect of displacement; both among those who moved out as well as those who moved in. The (NER) thus became a diaspora of a multiplicity of ethnicities (Alam, 2003).

Ethnicity and Social Exclusion

The NER is home to more than 400 distinct ethnic groups and sub-groups, out of which 119 ethnic groups are recognized by our constitution as “Scheduled Tribes”. Moreover, a diverse non-tribal population also inhabits Assam, Manipur and Tripura. The numbers of insurgency groups in this region are also very large. Wolf (2006) argues that it is not purely ethnic or nationalistic issues that cause conflict. When legitimate socio-political and economic grievances of disadvantaged ethnic groups are unheard of and unaddressed over long periods, ethnic conflicts occur. Such conflicts stem from ethnopolitical assertion and social inequality. Ethnicity and conflict, are also rooted in land and resources, especially in the NER, with a history of politically induced migration and movements based on hegemony (Shimray & Devi, 2009). A misbalance in human relationships continues to drive the ethnicity induced upheavals. It has now assumed a character of permanence; a state of existence; and even a state of mind. A feeling of oppression becomes a lived experience, burdened further by a lack of development and opportunities in the region, giving rise to social exclusion.

Bossert et al. (2007) assert that prolonged and relative deprivation of access to certain functions of the social and political economy results in an overwhelming feeling of social exclusion. They also exemplify two basic elements of deprivation; namely, the inability to identify freely and fairly with

other members of society; and, the collective alienation one experiences as opposed to those not facing deprivation or exclusion. It is also highlighted that deprivation may be static but social exclusion is dynamic. A persistent increase in deprivation can make an individual socially excluded. Thus, space and time are both very significant in measuring and understanding social exclusion.

Nevile (2007) also reiterates the need for understanding social exclusion concerning deprivation. He rationalises landlessness and lack of access to the credit market as factors that can trigger impoverishment, deprivation, and exclusion. He also talks about 'active exclusion' and 'passive exclusion'. The former is when Government policies and programmes are designed to exclude certain people from it. The latter happens when there is no such deliberate attempt but the benefits continue to evade them. The NER is more of the latter. He adds that social exclusion is reflected when an individual's access to functioning is persistently denied; both in absolute and relative terms, as compared with the rest of society.

Berman and Phillips (2000) talk about social exclusion in the context of lack of social participation, integration, and power. They argue that social exclusion erodes the 'collective values' and 'the social fabric' and underline the spatial and temporal contexts in determining social exclusion. The multi-dimensional aspects of it and the OECD social indicators while mapping social exclusion must be considered. They illustrate how equal opportunity, poverty, health, education, learning, employment, income, quality of life, access to goods and services, safety and risks issues, attachment with the new social environment are significant determinants.

Bijukumar (2013) asserts that nation-states play a major role in the context of exclusionary practices when certain ethnic communities are left out of standard normative practices. Wimmer (2006) explains this exclusionary strategy by arguing that the minorities are invariably left out from the national imagination but continue to dwell inside the state.

Free India was irrelevant to these smaller sub nationalities of the NER as they felt suppressed. Feelings of social exclusion was a consequence of a myopic nation-building process. Traditional ethnic frontiers were subsumed in arbitrariness. It was amidst this angst that the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution was conceptualised, recognizing the need for autonomy of district councils and the significance of traditional institutions (Bijukumar, 2013). Despite all these positive discriminations, the tribal ethnic

communities continue to be antagonistic as various kinds of exclusion mar their integration process.

Ethnicity and Exclusivity

The civil strife and unrest that prevails in the NER attribute itself to multiple ethnicities and their aspirations to have exclusive rights over specific homelands singularly. To this, Goswami (2007) reiterates that in a multi-ethnic place like the NER, it is near impossible to decide which ethnicity could be given an exclusive homeland. She also attributes the roots of the problem to the colonial rulers, who were detached from the ground realities of the region. Their policies were based purely on cursory knowledge of the people and commercial gain remained their significant motive. Another cruel perspective was that some communities were best left outside the purview of modern administration; labelling them as excluded or backward. The Indian government continued with this poorly derived exclusionary framework. Perhaps, the idea was that such excluded communities will grow at their own pace and gradually merge into the mainstream.

However, this appears to have been unviable. Goswami (2007) further informs us that over and above the sixth schedule, the policy of ethnic reformation of the NER around the 1960s has backfired in the form of internal disintegration, an explosion of ethnic identity movements, and secession. 1960 onwards, Assam was disintegrated and four states came out of it. Except for Arunachal, Manipur, and Tripura, all the other states in the NER were thus carved out hoping to keep insurgent and secessionist activities at bay. However, in the process of reorganisation, the state boundaries of almost all the NE states were not defined clearly enough to pre-empt the possibility of inter-state border disputes. Accordingly, there have been huge consequences in terms of uprooting of populations which have been attributed to unsuccessful counter-insurgency measures, consequently leaving large civilian populations displaced.

Bhaumik (2014) has also reiterated that attempting to put an end to the region's multiple insurgencies that is debilitating the vital resources of the NER more specifically and of India as a whole, could be a fine way to contain forceful migration and promote development in the NER. He has emphasised that India can enhance its global image by attending to its domestic problems adeptly and free it from ethnic uprisings and secessionist movements. Thus, the regime in Delhi must truly act in tandem with its rhetoric of "Act East" policy where the NER is strategically placed and taken into confidence as well. Balancing and decentralising the urbanisation process will also go a long way in checking uncontrolled migration to urban centres which are fast

spawning a multitude of slums, thus resulting in the degenerative face of development.

Gender and Displacement

The scale of the impact of displacement on women is oft-neglected. Merely enlisting them as vulnerable and hardest hit in terms of numbers does not suffice if we must understand the gender context. Dasgupta and Dey (2010) emphasize the glaring negligence of the gender dimension while examining development vis-a-vis displacement. Conflict over common property resources (CPRs) uproots their lives and livelihoods. They uphold a report of the North Eastern Social Research Council (NESRC) which highlights the displacement of five to six crores of people owing to CPR conflicts. In Assam, CPRs comprised 10 lakh acres out of 14 lakh acres acquired for development projects. Such instances disempower the woman and usurp her usufructuary rights over the CPRs. The rehabilitation process is fixated on the male and the woman's condition deteriorates as her livelihood is lost. Jobs also do not come easy as often the women have none or minimal education. The lower castes and women are denied of most skilled or semi-skilled jobs and get the perfunctory unskilled jobs. Cultural role expectations also impinge upon the woman more. Conflict resolution committees do not co-opt women. Drop-outs of girl children are higher in conflict zones. Thus, incorporating a gender discourse into policies and making them part of key decision-making bodies are the need of the hour.

Conclusions

The migration and displacement problem are a typically complex problem in the NER. Intervention measures have been proposed in terms of a historical atlas of migrants. It remains an effort in the right direction but it is easier said than done. Containing ethnic strife through militarisation also is a poor option. Development projects too come with their woes of upsetting the ecological balance. The NER is lined with multiple ethnicities where each one is fiercely protective of their identities. Thus, in the given scenario, an active securitisation of the international borders must be given prime importance. Local self-governing bodies can provide a supportive network in this regard. The media and the government's obsession only with transnational refugees, development induced displacement, and armed conflict must give way to one that is more all-encompassing and composite in its approach; rather than tackling them in isolation. The multiple factors that induce migration and displacement intersect with each other at various levels. Those displaced must be given easy access to more humane ways of resettlement and rehabilitation

so that they can rebuild their lives gradually. Moreover, the scale of internally displaced people in the NER is very high. In order to arrest these spawning numbers, long-lasting peace in the region is the only way out. Both state and non-state actors need to handhold each other towards this goal.

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